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“Biochemistry in Biotechnology”

Foreword

Dear colleagues

Welcome to the XII Conference of The Serbian Biochemical Society, entitled 'Biochemistry in Biotechnology'.

This year we have the richest program ever. In addition to our tradition to invite promising young researchers from four main university centers in Serbia to deliver lectures, we have eight guests from abroad that will participate through FEBS3+ program or within ANSO PRESSION project. This is a turning point in the organization of the conference which undergoes a transformation into scientific event with strong international character.

As always, we cherish the participation of PhD students and early career researchers. We are glad that many colleagues took the opportunity to show what they do and to find their place within the scientific ecosystem.

Organizing Committee

Phenolic profile, antioxidant and antidiabetic potential of traditionally prepared sage and peppermint juices

Sanja Krstić^{1*}, Saša Vukmirović³, Sanja Berežni², Nebojša Stilinović³, Nebojša Pavlović⁴

¹*Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences, University of Graz, Austria*

²*Department of Chemistry, Biochemistry and Environmental Protection, Faculty of Sciences, University of Novi Sad, Serbia*

³*Department of Pharmacology, Toxicology and Clinical Pharmacology, Faculty of Medicine, University of Novi Sad*

⁴*Department of Pharmacy, Faculty of Medicine, University of Novi Sad*

**e-mail sanja.krstic@uni-graz.at*

Sage and peppermint have a number of biological properties that have been demonstrated to be helpful for the treatment of a range of diseases. Determination of phenolic profile and the investigation of the biological activity of traditionally made juices obtained from sage and peppermint leaves origin from one village in Republic of Montenegro was the main goal of the present study. Phenolic compounds have been quantified using LC-MS/MS technique. The most abundant phenolics in the sample of traditional sage juice were quinic acid ($2571.86 \pm 1.15 \mu\text{g/g}$) and apigenin-7-O-glucoside ($324.36 \pm 1.15 \mu\text{g/g}$). Only two phenolic acids (caffeic and quinic) have been quantified, in significantly lower amount, in peppermint juice. In experimental mice (*Mus musculus*, NMRI Haan strain), the anti-diabetic (oral glucose tolerance and streptozotocin induced diabetes test) and antioxidant activity (measuring oxidative stress-related enzymes including superoxide-dismutase, catalase, glutathione peroxidase, glutathione reductase and glutathione-S-transferase and level of lipid peroxidation in liver homogenates) were examined. In both healthy and diabetic animals, a ten-day treatment with the tested juices caused the blood glucose level to decrease. Furthermore, the juices demonstrated notable antioxidant activity, which has boosted the activity of antioxidant enzymes and decreased the level of lipid peroxidation. The obtained results support traditional use of sage and peppermint juice as food with health and nutritional benefits.